

Opsoclonus-Myoclonus Syndrome in Chikungunya Virus Infection: A Case Report

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ABSTRACT

Chikungunya is an alphavirus transmitted primarily by mosquito vectors *Aedes aegypti* and *Aedes albopictus*. Chikungunya disease is epidemic in many parts of the world. The clinical spectrum of this disease range from fever, rash, arthralgia to neurologic complications like encephalitis and rarely death. During the 2016 epidemic of Chikungunya in Delhi, we came across an extremely rare neurological disorder of Opsoclonus-Myoclonus syndrome (OMS) in association with Chikungunya infection. The association of OMS with Chikungunya infection has not been reported previously in the literature. We report a case of a middle-aged gentleman who presented with areflexic quadriparesis and encephalopathy. Subsequently, he developed a continuous saccadic movement of both eyes with intermittent jerking of limbs. He was managed with supportive therapy which included mechanical ventilatory support, plasmapheresis and antiepileptic medications with which he improved and was discharged to home on tracheostomy tube in-situ.

KEYWORDS Chikungunya, Encephalitis, Opsoclonus-Myoclonus Syndrome

INTRODUCTION

Chikungunya fever is considered to cause a self-limiting illness characterized by fever, arthralgia and myalgia. However unusual neurological manifestations in the form of encephalopathy, seizures, neuropathies and meningoencephalitis are also seen. These unusual manifestations of the disease are better recognized during the outbreaks. There is no clear evidence to suggest whether these manifestations are due to persistence of virus in central nervous system or due to abnormal immune response [1]. During the recent epidemic of Chikungunya in Delhi, we came across an extremely rare neurological disorder of Opsoclonus-Myoclonus syndrome (OMS) in association with Chikungunya infection which has not been reported previously in the literature.

CASE REPORT

A 54-year-old diabetic and a hypertensive gentleman presented with two days history of high-grade fever, arthralgia, generalized myalgia and weakness in all four limbs. Blood-exams revealed thrombocytopenia (RBC $4.58 \times 10^6/\mu\text{L}$, Haemoglobin 13.3 g/dL, Platelets $87.00 \times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$, WBC: $7.8 \times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$, Neutrophils 86%, Lymphocytes 07%). A detailed neurological examination was done which revealed proximal weakness in lower limbs and hyperesthesia. Medical Research Council (MRC) scale [2] was used for the estimation of muscle power strength. His deep tendon reflexes were absent. On evaluation, his Nerve Conduction Study (NCS) demonstrated severe axonal motor sensory neuropathy in all four limbs, and Cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) analysis showed albuminocytological dissociation (total count 08 cells/mm³ with all mononuclear cells and proteins 106.5 mg/dl). Given these findings, a diagnosis of Guillain-Barre syndrome (GBS) was made, and plasmapheresis was initiated. On day 2 of admission, his neurological status deteriorated. His MRI brain and electroencephalography (EEG) were normal with no epileptiform activity.

Meanwhile, RT-PCR sent on day 1 for CHIK returned positive, confirming CHIK infection induced GBS and encephalopathy. Dengue Virus IgM and IgG antibodies and NS1 antigen

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RTPCR:- Reverse transcriptase polymerase chain reaction, TPE: Therapeutic plasma exchange, LVEF: Left ventricle Ejection fraction, MRC: Medical research council grade of strength, GBS:- Guillan-Barre Syndrome, NCS: Nerve conduction studies, CSF: Cerebrospinal Fluid, MRI Brain: Magnetic Resonance Imaging of Brain, EEG: Electroencephalography

Figure 1: Timeline of clinical features and interventions in RTPCR confirmed case of Chikungunya Virus infection during recent outbreak in Delhi, India, September 2016.

were all negative. Due to worsening of GCS and respiratory distress, he was put on invasive mechanical ventilatory support. On the 6th day of admission, the patient started having rapid abnormal, involuntary multivectorial chaotic conjugate eye movement associated with brief jerking of the left arm. He was sequentially started on intravenous levetiracetam, sodium valproate and clonazepam but with no response. On the 7th day, he had atrial fibrillation transiently which was terminated by intravenous amiodarone and potassium replacement. Two-dimensional echocardiography was done which revealed reduced left ventricular ejection fraction of 25% without any regional wall motion abnormality and normal cardiac biomarkers. A provisional diagnosis of viral myocarditis was made. Despite five cycles of TPE (Therapeutic Plasma Exchange), his neurological status remained the same. Therefore MRI brain was repeated which revealed acute multiple lacunar infarcts in bilateral Middle Cerebral Artery (MCA) region. He was started on systemic anticoagulation given atrial fibrillation and multiple acute infarcts. As the patient showed no improvement, two more sessions of TPE were done on the 9th and 10th day. Tracheostomy was done to facilitate weaning from the ventilator. Given constant abnormal movements involving eyes and limbs, tetrabenazine was also added. By the end of the third week, the patient started showing improvement in neurological status and eye movements, and he started following simple verbal commands. He was able to lift head, nodded and stuck tongue

out to verbal commands but continued to have flaccid limbs. By the end of the fourth week, opsoclonus reduced significantly and eventually stopped completely. The patient also started having some movement of upper limbs (MRC grade-3) and lower limbs (MRC grade-2). By fifth week his tracheostomy tube was changed to a speaking tracheostomy tube. He was discharged to ward for the occupational and physical therapy program. The patient was successfully discharged to home on day 35 of admission in fully conscious, a well-oriented state with Medical Research Council (MRC) of grade 4 in upper limbs and MRC of grade 3 in lower limbs with tracheostomy tube in-situ. The graphical representation of events in this case is summarized in Figure 1.

DISCUSSION

OMS is a rare autoimmune condition characterized by cerebellar degeneration and is seen in patients with encephalitis secondary to various etiologies such as cancers, toxins, autoimmune diseases, and viral infections [3]. OMS is associated with certain viral infections such as West Nile virus, Dengue virus, HIV, Enterovirus, Cytomegalovirus, Hepatitis C and Epstein Barr Virus [3]. OMS is thought to be autoimmune in origin. The underlying mechanisms of the opsoclonus are not well known. Leigh and Zee suggested dysfunction in one of the groups of neurons controlling the ocular motility in the reticular formation of the brain stem [3]. During the Chikungunya epidemic in Delhi in August-

September 2016, we saw a fulminant form of Chikungunya fever when many patients presented with neurological manifestations, i.e. encephalitis, seizures, axonal neuropathies and some even succumbed to the disease. Abnormal movements of body ranging from myoclonic jerks to seizures have been described during Chikungunya virus infection, but abnormal chaotic eye movements such as opsoclonus have not been described till date. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first reported case of OMS occurring in association with a Chikungunya virus infection. The occurrence of Guillan-Barre syndrome which is known to have autoimmune pathogenesis along with OMS in our patient points towards the likely autoimmune mechanism. Both Clonazepam and Valproic acid [4] was tried in our patient based on case reports after no response to immunotherapy. There was considerable improvement in opsoclonus-myoclonus in our patient after administration of tetrabenazine [4]. Tetrabenazine which reversibly depletes dopamine in the brain was used due to its anti-chorea efficacy [5]. More research is needed to elucidate the precise pathogenesis of OMS, so that specific treatment options are recommended.

CONCLUSION

Chikungunya virus can lead to varied neurological manifestations of which meningoencephalitis is very common. This case is probably the first report of an opsoclonus-myoclonus syndrome that occurred during the Chikungunya fever. This case report provides some evidence regarding the neurotropic behaviour of CHIKV. However, we still need a conclusive proof for its neurotropism. Through this case study, we would like to increase the awareness regarding the rare but debilitating and reversible neurological manifestation of Opsoclonus-Myoclonus syndrome in patients of Chikungunya infection.

PATIENT CONSENT

Written informed consent was obtained from the patient for publication of this case report and any accompanying images. A copy of the written consent is available for review by the Editor-in-Chief of this journal.

COMPETING INTERESTS

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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